

1982 kharif. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Punshi was the test variety.

Six granular herbicides were broadcast 5 days after transplanting. Untreated and

nonweeded plots were the control. Weeds/m² were counted at harvest and disease intensity was scored using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Thiobencarb controlled weeds best, followed by butachlor. However, heavy

NBI infection was observed in thiobencarb-treated plots, which resulted in the lowest yield (see table). Increased NBI infection may have been caused by changes in the metabolic processes of the rice plants. □

Effect of fungicides on neck blast infection and rice yield

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Neck blast (NBI) of rice caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. is a serious problem in Manipur. We studied the relative efficacy

of six fungicides for NBI control in wet fields in 1982.

Fungicides carbendazim, benomyl, ziram, captafol, mancozeb, and edifenphos were sprayed at tillering, leaf booting, and just after flowering. Control plots were sprayed with sterile water. Percent infected panicles was calculated at maturity. Edifenphos-treated plots had no infection and yielded most, followed by those treated with ziram (see table). □

Effect of fungicides on NBI and yield, mean of three replications, Wangbal, Manipur, India.

Fungicide	Application rate (kg or liters/ha)	Infection (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Carbendazim	0.5	12.1	2.35
Benomyl	0.5	4.3	2.67
Ziram	2.5	3.6	2.91
Captafol	2.0	23.5	2.05
Mancozeb	2.5	21.1	2.10
Edifenphos	1.0	0	3.50
Control		27.2	1.95

Association of two types of virus particles in an isolate of rice tungro disease

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Late planted Jaya exhibited 90 to 100% tungro disease incidence in Orissa during 1982 kharif. Disease identity was established by transmission tests of the vector *Nephotettix virescens*. We studied tungro-infested plants under an electron microscope at the CNRA.

Dip preparations in 1% neutral phosphotungstic acid (PTA), made from sap of

different parts of infected leaves, were observed under an EM 300 Philips electron microscope. Isometric virus particles about 28 nm in diam and bacilliform virus particles measuring about 33 nm in diam and 175 nm long were observed (see figure). In different samples, bacilliform virus particles and isometric virus particles were in ratios 1:10 and 1:11. Observations indicated that both isometric and bacilliform virus particles are associated with severe tungro symptoms in the Cuttack isolate, which also is true for isolates from several other South and Southeast Asian countries.

Observations using negative coloration of samples, made from crude sap of infected leaves in PTA, indicate a lower percentage of bacilliform particles than of isometric particles. However, our electron microscope observations of

Electron micrograph showing tungro isometric (I) and tungro bacilliform (B) virus in dip preparations from leaf sap infected with rice tungro disease from Cuttack, India. Virus particles were negatively stained with 1% neutral PTA (magnification 54000 X).

purified virus preparations indicated that negative staining with PTA does not allow a correct estimate of the two types of virus particles, perhaps because PTA preparations damage bacilliform particles. □

Pest management and control INSECTS

Some common predators of rice insect pests in Assam, India

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Assam is a tropical rain forest area with green vegetation throughout the year. Rainfall is 1,400-1,800 mm, humidity averages 85-95%, and temperature is 20-30°C during the monsoon (Jun-Sep), which is the main rice growing season. Monsoon conditions favor rice cultiva-

tion, pest multiplication, and the proliferation of their natural enemies. Predators, particularly arthropods, are abundant and play a significant role in controlling major insect pests of rice.

From 1980 to 1982, we evaluated monsoon rice to determine the role of

natural enemies (see table). The Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London, and the Systematics Section of

the Entomology Division, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi, identified the specimens. □

Common predators of rice insect pests recorded 1980-82 in Assam, India.

Predators	Prey	Prevalence or intensity
I. Araneae (spiders)		
Tetragnathidae <i>Tetragnatha mandibulata</i>	Nymphs and adults of <i>Cofana spectra</i> , <i>C. yasumatsui</i> , <i>Nephotettix virescens</i> , <i>N. nigropictus</i> , and <i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	High
Oxyopidae <i>Oxyopes javanus</i> Thorell	-do-	High
Araneidae <i>Neoscona theisi</i> (Walckenaer)	-do-	Moderate
<i>Araneus</i> sp.	-do-	-do-
Lycosidae <i>Pardosa</i> sp.	-do-	Low
II. Odonata (dragonflies)		
Libellulidae <i>Orthetrum sabina</i> (Dowry)	Adults of <i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> , <i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> and <i>N. fluctuosalis</i>	High
<i>Crocothemis servilia</i> (Dowry)	-do-	-do-
<i>Pantala flavescens</i> (Fabricius)	-do-	Moderate
<i>Diplacodes nebulosa</i> (Fabricius)	-do-	-do-
III. Odonata (damselflies)		
Coenagrionidae <i>Ischnura delicata</i> Dis	Nymphs and adults of <i>Nephotettix virescens</i> , <i>N. nigropictus</i> , <i>Cofana spectra</i> , and <i>Sogatella furcifera</i> .	High
<i>Ischnura rofostigma</i> Selys	-do-	-do-
<i>Agriocnemis pygmaea</i> Rambur	-do-	Moderate
<i>Ceriagrion coromandelianum</i> (Fabricius)	-do-	Low
IV. Orthoptera (meadow grasshopper)		
Tettigoniidae <i>Conocephalus longipennis</i> (de Haan)	Nymphs and adults of <i>Nephotettix</i> sp. and <i>Recilia dorsalis</i>	Moderate
V. Hemiptera (predaceous bugs)		
Pentatomidae <i>cicrona caerulea</i> Linnaeus	Larvae of <i>Naranga diffusa</i> , <i>Mythimna separata</i> , <i>Spodoptera mauritia</i> , and <i>S. litura</i> .	Moderate
<i>Andrallus spinidens</i> Fabricius	-do-	Low
Pygomenida benghalensis (Westwood)	Adults of <i>Di cladispa armigera</i>	Moderate
<i>Menida histrio</i> F.)		
Reduviidae <i>Coranus</i> sp.	Larvae of <i>Naranga</i> sp. and <i>Spodoptera</i> sp.	Moderate
VI. Diptera (rubber fly)		
Asilidae <i>Promachus</i> sp.	Nymphs and adults of <i>Oxya fuscovittata</i>	Moderate
VII. Coleoptera (beetles)		
Cicindelidae <i>Cicindela sexpunctata</i> Fabricius	Nymphs and adults of <i>Leptocorisa acuta</i> and <i>L. oratoria</i>	Moderate
Carabidae <i>Casnoidae indica</i> Thumberg	Nymphs of planthoppers and leafhoppers	-do-
Coccinellidae <i>Micraspis discolor</i> Fabricius	Nymphs and adults of <i>Cofana</i> sp.	High
<i>Harmonia octomaculata</i> Fabricius	<i>Nephotettix</i> sp. and <i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	Low
-do-	-do-	Low
VIII. Hymenoptera (wasps)		
Sphecidae <i>Psenulus</i> sp. nr. <i>Aogatophagus</i> P.	Nymphs and adults of leafhoppers	Low

A simple technique for locating feeding sites of green leafhopper in rice plants

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The feeding behavior of the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) on susceptible and resistant rice varieties is not yet clearly understood. Although GLH is regarded as a phloem feeder on susceptible rice varieties and a xylem feeder on resistant varieties, the existing semiquantitative biochemical methodologies for locating GLH feeding sites are complicated. We tested a simple technique for monitoring GLH feeding using a dye that is selectively translocated in xylem vessels.

GLH-susceptible TN1 and resistant ASD7 were grown separately in clay pots in a greenhouse. When seedlings were 10 d old, they were carefully removed from the pots and roots were washed thoroughly to remove soil particles. Roots were then immersed in an aqueous solution of 0.2% Safranin O (Kansai Reagent Corp.,

1. Assembly for collecting GLH honeydew, IRRI 1983.